

FACTORS MOTIVATING THE ESTABLISHMENT OF *WAQF* INSTITUTION TOWARDS POVERTY ALLEVIATION AMONG MUSLIM *UMMAH* IN OYO STATE, SOUTH WEST, NIGERIA

About the Authors

- 1- **Ibraheem Alani AbdulKareem** is a PhD student of Islamic Finance and Banking, Faculty of Business and Management, Universiti Sultan Zainal Abidin (UNISZA). +60103855676. Corresponding author: ibraheemalani@yahoo.com
- 2- **Ahamad Faosiy Ogunbado** is a PhD, Senior lecture in Faculty of Islamic Development Management, Universiti Islam Sultan Sharif Ali (UNISSA).
- 3- **AbdulFattah AbdulGaniyy** PhD, Department of Accountancy, Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda, Zamfara State, Nigeria.
- 4- **Mohd Sadad bin Mahmud** is a PhD, Senior lecturer in Faculty of Business and Management, Universiti Sultan Zainal Abidin (UNISZA), 23100, Gong Badak, Terengganu, Malaysia.

ABSTRACT

This article explores the factors motivating the establishment of waqf institution towards poverty alleviation among Muslim Ummah in Oyo state, South West, Nigeria. The importance of waqf institutions is to take care of the needs of the less privileged in the society. To achieve the objective of this study, the theory of planned behaviour (TPB) was selected to accommodate such as attitude, subjective norm and perceived behavioural control as predictors of waqf institutions establishment in Oyo state, Nigeria. Based on this, three hypotheses were formulated for the study. This study adopts a quantitative research where a sample was drawn from the population of Islamic scholar (Alfa) in Oyo state, Nigeria. A number of 218 Islamic scholars were randomly selected to respond to the survey which was designed to examine the relationship between the predictors (attitude, subjective norm and perceived behavioural control) and the establishment of waqf institution as a way of poverty alleviation. Data analysis using statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 22 software and statistical analyses like Pearson correlation and Regression was employed to achieve the objective of this study. The findings supported the three formulated hypotheses, which indicate that attitude, subjective norm and perceived behavioural control have a positive significant relationship towards the establishment of waqf institution as a way of poverty alleviation. This study adds to the existing literature of waqf and suggests opportunities for future research.

Keywords: Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), Waqf Institution, Poverty Alleviation.

1. Introduction

The increasing rate of poverty in the world especially in the developing countries like Nigeria calls for concern. The concern is so terrible in Nigeria with an average Nigerian described as a poor man (Okoroafor & Nwaeze, 2013). This ravaging phenomenon of poverty has attracted the attention of different scholars and authorities to seek different perspectives of combating the menace. Scholars are yet to agree on the definition of poverty (John & Bright, 2012). The United Nation Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) (2016) describes poverty from the economic point

of view, that it is a condition when a family's income fails to meet a federally established threshold that differs across countries. According to John and Bright (2012), such condition leads to a sense of helplessness, dependence, and lack of opportunity, self-confidence, and self-respect on the part of the poor.

Literature and documentary evidence have shown that *Waqf* is one of the important mechanisms for the alleviation of poverty. The concept of *waqf* is derived from an Arabic word وقف: الوقوف "opposite site, stall on the place, (Lisan al-Arab, 630-711H). Etymologically, it implies "causing

a thing to stop and standstill". It also implies to make it dependent on, detention, holding, stop and keeping (Baalbaki, 1988). From Islamic law point of view, *waqf* implies holding properties, assets or belongings in the custody of an Islamic entity meant specifically to see to the needs of the poor and needy.

Having identified the problem of poverty by the government of Nigeria, different measures have been taken in the past to curb the menace. However, these measures have not yielded the fruitful result. For instance, the poverty rate in Nigeria has been relatively increasing from the 1980s.

According to the current Vice President of Nigeria over 100m Nigerians living below poverty line regardless of past government policies to curb poverty and improve welfare of the citizens. He additionally identified that policies by the previous government were wrongly articulated and the outcome did not have direct impact on the country (Uzoh, 2016). Also, World Bank reports postulated that Nigeria is set to turn into the world third biggest poverty by 2050 (Kazeem, 2018). The rate in 2010, as indicated in Table 1.1, was 69% which translated into 112.47 million Nigerians as living in poverty.

Table 1.1
Poverty rate in Nigeria from 1980-2010

Year	Estimated population (Million)	Moderately poor (%)	Extremely poor (%)	Total (%)	Population in poverty (Million)
1980	65	21.0	6.2	27.2	17.1
1985	75	34.2	12.1	46.3	34.7
1992	91.5	28.9	13.9	42.8	39.2
1996	102.3	36.3	29.3	65.6	67.1
2004	126.3	32.4	22.0	54.4	68.7
2010	163	30.3	38.7	69	112.47
2015				46.8	
2016				48.4	

Source: National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2010).

Despite its huge oil riches and moving economic development, Nigeria has struggled to kick its people out of poverty over the years. The viewpoints from the World Bank's 2017 Atlas of Sustainable Development Goals indicates that 35 million more Nigerians were breathing in extreme poverty in 2013 which was higher than in 1990. The Atlas tracks the advance nations are making to meet 17 improvement objectives set out by the United Nations, for example, decreasing

economic imbalance, the utilization of clean energy, and literacy rates. Among the 10 most crowded nations for which information is available, just only Nigeria recorded an increase in the number of citizens who live in extreme poverty over the time of the study. The Atlas describes "extreme poverty" as living on under \$1.90 per day (World Bank Group, 2017). Nigeria still has the largest population of extreme poverty.

Data: World Poverty Clock.

N/S		Poverty
1	Income share held by highest 20%	49 %
2	Income share held by second 20%	9.7 %
3	Population living in slums (% of urban population)	50.2 %
4	Income share held by third 20%	14.4 %
5	Poverty headcount ratio at national poverty line (% of population)	46 %
6	Number of poor at \$1.90 a day (2011 PPP) (millions)	84.8%
7	Poverty headcount ratio at \$2 a day (PPP) (% of population)	76.46 %
8	Number of poor at \$3.10 a day (2011 PPP) (millions)	122

AbulHasan (2002) posits that *Waqf* as a long-lasting form of charity characterised by perpetuity is capable of reducing poverty problem. He further argues that the institution of *waqf* is such a perpetual charity in the Islamic ethical system that alleviates poverty menace. In a like manner, Yusuff & Nor Aziza (2013) state that poverty alleviation requires a financial system in form of small, medium and large-scale enterprises, investment, partnership, micro-financing, interest-free loan among others. They argue that

poverty can be alleviated through *waqf* properties. This implies that, if the donors are well prepared, committed, dedicated and wish to donate part of their assets for *waqf* in taking care of the needy, irrespective of their tribe, gender, sect, and colour; poverty will reduce.

As reported by Monzer (2003), another area to note is that the action to performing *waqf* is not compulsory as compared to *zakat*, which becomes compulsory on a Muslim when his or her asset wealth reaches a certain amount (*Nisab*). The

institution of *Waqf* may play a good role to bridge the gap between those who are in need and those who are capable to give through contribution in cash or kind or movable and immovable assets by, and the aggregate contribution towards taking care of the underprivileged.

Therefore, this study, intends to examine the impact of *Waqf* on poverty alleviation in Oyo state south-west, Nigeria. Oyo State is one of the states in Nigeria, it has a population of over five million, and it is located in the South West, Nigeria, with its capital in Ibadan. It also has thirty-three Local Governments (National Population Commission, 2010). Ogunbado (2013) state that Oyo State is one of Yorubaland state along with Lagos, Ekiti, Ondo, Ogun, Osun and the state is one of the oldest states in the country. Its capital is the largest city

2. Literature Review

Waqf is one of the ancient charity institutions in the globe and the initiative dated back to the lifetime of the Holy Prophet (S A W). A prophetic narration revealed that during the life of the Holy Prophet (SAW), Umar Ibn Khatab made an inquiry on how he should arrange a piece of property and the Prophet answered by saying “preserve the thing itself and devote its fruit for a religious purpose.” According to this narration, Umar Ibn Khatab, withheld the property from being sold or willed out, rather the property was held for commercial purpose and the income generated was used for charity purpose. This action of Umar ibn Khatab was cited as the first example of *waqf* in Islam (Bremer, 2004).

Kahf (1998) gives a comprehensive account of what *waqf* is all about. He defined *waqf* as holding an asset and preventing its consumption for purpose of repeatedly extracting its usufruct for the benefit of an object representing righteousness/philanthropy. Saifuddin,

in West Africa. The state is bounded in the north side by Kwara state, in the east side by Osun state, in the south by Ogun state and in the west by the Republic of Benin. Oyo State cover the land area around 28, 454 square kilometres of land mass (Adeyonu Oni, Okoruwa & Omonona 2012).

The objective of this study is to examine how the domain of TPB influence the establishment of *waqf* institution toward poverty alleviation. The paper is organized as follow: After the introduction, section two deals with literature review, historical background of *waqf* and importance of *waqf* in poverty alleviation. Section three explains the methodology of the study. And the last section is based on findings and conclusion.

Kayadibi, Polat, Fidan, & Kayadibi (2014) define *waqf* as a property or asset donated by its owner for the sake of Allah in perpetuity (forever) to be used for charity for the benefit of Muslim Ummah. The scholars further stated that poverty is the major problem that faces many Muslim countries and agreed that *waqf* and *zakat* can be an alternative to tackle the problem. Cizakca (1998) stated that Muslims are encouraged to establish *waqf* institution that would encourage them to perform ongoing charity for many years even including periods after the death of the founder. Ali (2009) explain that establishment of *waqf* institution has played a major role in the improvement of the Muslims community wellbeing in the history of Islam. Therefore, the establishment of *waqf* institution is essential to the survival and the development of the Muslim *Ummah*. Foyasal (2010) described the role of *waqf* institution and the role of *waqf* fund in the alleviation of poverty in Bangladesh and its

contribution to the establishment of Dhaka University. *Waqf* institution plays a significant role in poverty alleviation with increasing social wellbeing activities. The social wellbeing role of *waqf* will be governed by their types and scope.

Waqf is of two types namely: Philanthropic and Religious. The philanthropic *waqf* has two categories of beneficiaries which are the public-philanthropic and family philanthropic. Only the Public philanthropic are important institutions for poverty alleviation. Ahmad Bello (2009) sees *waqf* as an essential part of Islamic civilization that takes care of the poor within the community. *Waqf* institution assists welfare development and keeps step with economic development in the community. It represents an asset dedicated in perpetuity for a particular beneficiary or group of beneficiaries to attain specific purposes. The encouragement of establishing such a socioeconomic movement is in line with *Zakah*. The institution of *waqf* is not only successful and active throughout Islamic previous times but has contributed meaningfully to numerous social causes such as education, health, research and meeting the need of less privileged of the society. He further explains that the institution of *waqf* in the current socioeconomic setup should be seen as an extra source of the program involving poverty alleviation. The previous history of *waqf* recommends that the institution can be used to organize additional funds for needy sections of the community to address social issues such as Skill and micro-entrepreneurial development, Education, Healthcare and Water and sanitation facilities in the rural area. The last *waqf* posterity or family *waqf* surfaced after the Prophet (S A W) passed away, during the rule of Umar ibn Khattab (635-

645). The second Khalifah. Umar ibn Khattab decided to document in writing his *Waqf* in Khaybar, he called some of the companions of the Muhammad (S A W) to confirm this document. Many of those that engage in family *waqf* set a condition that the income and the fruit of their *waqf* must firstly be given to their own family and only the extras if anything left, should be given to the needy and poor. This type of *waqf* is called family *waqf* or posterity *waqf*. *Waqf* in Islamic community may also be for one's own offspring or family. Alongside the lines accepted by traditional *Fuqaha*, we discuss that the *waqf* family is charitable in spirit because it gives revenue/usufruct to people free of charge and improves the wellbeing of upcoming generations (Monzer 2003, Nour and Hassan (2012).

Mustafa and Ogunbado (2015) reported that *Waqf* properties create a large percentage of societal wealth in numerous Muslim nations. However, numerous Muslim nations are facing many socioeconomic problems such as illiteracy, poverty and lack of basic healthcare services. These socioeconomic issues urge contemporary Muslim scholars to restore the conventional methods of financing the growth of *waqf* properties to guarantee that *waqf* institution plays its vital role in enhancing the social welfare of the *ummah*. The practice of giving philanthropy for enhancing social welfare of others is significantly energized in Islam. According to the authors, over hundreds of years, *waqf* as a social foundation has played a great role in enhancing the social welfare of the Muslim communities and society at large. And it additionally opens an entryway for wealthier Muslim to be liberal and use their wealth in an appropriate way for the sake of Almighty Allah's pleasure and perpetual rewards.

Hisham (2013) further explains that: Muslims needed an institution that would enable them to perform all three of these good deeds. The institution was the waqf which can, indeed, assure on going, recurring charity for many years, even centuries, after the death of the founder; it can finance scholars whose lasting word would benefit mankind for a long period and the sawabs (good deeds) that would

According to the (Khan. nd) historically, the institution of *waqf* can be used for the poor and needy in the society by organizing extra resources to address the socioeconomic problems like: health, education, skills and micro-entrepreneurial growth, water and cleanness services in rural areas. The author is of the opinion that *waqf* can also maintain a fund, properly invested, and utilized during the famine and other crisis to help extremely poor to survive the crisis. A *waqf* can assist people in the perspective of nations with extreme poverty, facing starvation, death and sickness. He related that in the modern socioeconomic set-up the institution of

Osman (2012) further acknowledged that:
The essential element of *Waqaf* is that a person, with the intention of committing a pious deed, declares part of his or her property to be

Ahmed. et. al (2015) in their article examines the perception of Muslim society in Uganda on *Waqf* and its roles in socioeconomic. Furthermore, high rate of awareness among Muslim people in Uganda on *Waqf* and socio-economic roles would provide a platform for a religious authority to urge Muslims to give their wealth as *Waqf* for socio-economic improvement. For example, more hospitals and schools could be built and *Waqf*

accrue to them and would be shared by the waqf's founder who had provided for their sustenance in the first place; finally the management of the waqf can be entrusted to the offspring of the founder so that while, on the one hand, careful and loyal management is assured, on the other, the offspring would pray for the deceased for, thanks to his waqf, he or she is not in destitute (Hisham, 2013 p. 393).

waqf should be seen as an extra source to maintain the program concerning poverty alleviation. Jlil and Mohd Ramli. (2008) mention that *Waqf* as a charity instrument that is used to establish institutions like hospitals, universities and research centre that could generate income. The incomes generated from these institutions are distributed among the Muslim community. Khan (1998) gives a comprehensive account of what *waqf* is all about. He defines *Waqf* as holding an asset and preventing its consumption for the purpose of repeatedly extracting its usufruct for righteousness/philanthropy purpose.

henceforth unalienable and designates persons or public utilities as beneficiaries of its yields (Osman, 2012 p. 26).

organisation would be capable to provide microcredit finance for small-scale businesses. This, in turn, will enhance the social welfare, create employment and reduce poverty among Muslim society. The study shows that majority of respondents are aware of *Waqf* and its part of socio-economic growth. Nevertheless, the majority of the respondents did not know that *Waqf* can be created from movable property such as agricultural

products, livestock and financial. The authors emphasise that the Uganda community is facing many socio-economic problems such as lack of good healthcare, poverty and education. Thus, it is imperative for religious authorities to promote *waqf* to the Muslim community to ease their living and to raise fund for socio-economic improvement. *Waqf* is an act of refraining from the use and disposal of any asset from which one can benefit or perpetually use its proceeds for charity purpose (Mannan 2005).

Review of the Factors that Influence the Establishment of *Waqf* Institution Towards Poverty Alleviation & TPB.

This study employs Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) as its underpinning theory. Ajzen, (1991) extends the theory of reasoned action (TRA) as it answers the weakness that is inherent in the TRA (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975; Ajzen & Fishbein, 1980). In this regard, perceived behavioural control (PBC) which is one of the core variables of TPB is assessed by asking people of how much control they possessed while executing a particular behaviour. Importantly, the inclusion of TPB variables brings about tremendous improvements in desired behaviour. Moreover, it reveals people's feeling concerning the easiness or difficulty that is associated with the performance of a specific behaviour (Ajzen, 1991). These

Attitude

Attitude is setting up of the relationship between behaviour and belief (Fauziah et al., 2008). Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) defined attitude an individual's behaviour towards lawful or good activities. The scholars express that people's feeling, for example, negative or positive will influence the individual in playing out a specific behaviour. Also, the Theory Planned Behaviour (TPB), shows that

Similarly, Magda Ismail (2014) defined *Waqf* as the retention of an asset immovable or movable, by an organizer and the perseverance of its benefit in permanence to the recipients.

In summary, *Waqf* is a form of donation that is religiously encouraged as an act of worship in Islam and involves the holding of properties, assets or one's belongings in the custody of an Islamic entity meant solely to meet the needs of the poor and needy (Noor Faezah, 2014; Mardiyah, 2014).

theories, in essence, describe human behaviour under diverse situations. Consequently, taking the TPB into consideration, intention and feeling of control which individual holds is used to determine behaviour, whereas their attitudes, PBC and subjective norms influence intentions.

The issues which influence the establishment of the *waqf* institution toward poverty alleviation are attitude, subjective norm, perceived behavioural control, religiosity and amount of information. The explanation of each variable will be clarified in this part. All these external variables will explain the relationship between dependent variable and independent variables consistent with the previous researchers.

attitude has an important relationship with the individual behaviour.

Using Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) Osman (2014) affirms the suitability of TPB in understanding the *waqf* establishment and found its support among educated people. Clearly, attitude is significantly related to *waqf* establishment that will lead to poverty alleviation. This result is in line with the findings of

previous studies, for example, Lada et al., (2008); Amin and Chong, (2011).

Subjective Norm

Social influence is regarded as the subjective norm which is a construct that is unique to TPB. Importantly, subjective norm influences the individual behaviour and social environment (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975).

Ajzen (1991) defines subjective norms as the perceived of the influence of friends or relatives with regards to whether the certain behaviour should be performed. It alludes to an individual's view of applicable options from others on whether

to execute specific behaviour. Past studies, for example, Shih Fang (2004), Lada et al. (2008) and Amin and Chong (2011) have found the significance and impact of subjective norm on the establishment of *waqf* institution. For instance, Lada et al. (2008) look at the impact of subjective norm and the establishment of *waqf* institution. This study shows that "environment" can be a major factor explaining why person performs some behaviour.

Perceived Behavioural Control

Perceived behavioural control refers to the level of capacity and control which an individual perceives over performing the desired behaviour (Ajzen, 1991). Ajzen (2002) found that PBC has a direct influence on behaviour and indirect influence on behaviour via intention anchored on the assumption that an individual is going to be motivated to execute his behavioural intention (Ajzen, 2002). In line with the argument of Madden et al. (1992), it is possible for an individual to possess favourable attitudes and/or social influence to perform the behaviour, his intention however to execute such a behaviour may be reduced if he has not enough information or other resources at his disposal to kick off the

behaviour. In essence, there is a tendency that an individual is going to perform certain behaviour if he believes that he has the required ability and is confident to perform it. Previous studies have reported the significant influence of PBC in different fields (Bhattacharjee, 2000; Armitage, 2005). For instance, in the case of participation in *waqf* scheme, one would expect that an individual who believes that he has the resources, like to have better perceptions that he is in control and therefore, his behavioural intentions may increase. It is expected to generalize the significant influence of PBC to the establishment of *waqf* Institutions toward poverty alleviation

3. Research Methodology

This study uses a cross-sectional design with emphasis on survey method. Cross-sectional design involves gathering data once over a period of days, weeks or months in order to meet the research objective (Cavana, *et al.*, 2001). The method is desirable because it is an excellent method of obtaining information about what people believed that can

influence their behaviour, and the respondents' attitudes and characteristics (Keyton, 2015). The research design is vital to identify the outcome from the respondent by answering the questionnaire which relate to the dependent (establishment of *waqf* institution as a way for poverty alleviation) and independent variables comprising attitude, subjective

norm, religiosity, perceived behavioural control and amount of information. The outcome of the survey is suitable to measure the relationship between dependent variable and independent variables.

This aspect deals with the diagrammatical presentation of the relationship between the three independent variables comprising

Figure 1. Research framework

attitude, subjective norm and perceived behavioural control; and the dependent variable (establishment of Waqf institution as a way for poverty alleviation) is equally shown in the diagram. The framework, as depicted in Figure 1 below indicates that the three independent variables influence the establishment of *waqf* institution toward poverty alleviation.

This employed three hypotheses to examine the impact *waqf* on poverty alleviation among Muslim *Ummah* in Oyo State South West of Nigeria.

The following hypotheses are formulated.

Hypothesis 1

H₁: There is a positive significant relationship between attitude and establishment of *waqf* institution as a way of poverty alleviation.

Hypothesis 2

Population

The population is the aggregate of items possessing a common trait or traits (Kotharin, 2004). It refers to the total entities qualified to be studied by the researcher (Marczyk *et al.*, 2005).

The population of this study, therefore, refers to the total number of Islamic scholars (Alfas means Islamic scholar in the Yoruba language) in Oyo state, south-west, Nigeria. This covers Islamic scholars

H₁: There is a positive significant relationship between subjective norm and establishment of *waqf* institution as a way of poverty alleviation.

Hypothesis 3

H₁: There is a positive significant relationship between Perceived Behavioural Control and establishment of *waqf* institution as a way of poverty alleviation.

in all local government areas of Oyo state, South West, Nigeria. In that part of Nigeria for instance, there is no provision for ministry of religious affairs; hence, it becomes difficult for the researcher to get the comprehensive list of all the Islamic scholars in the state. In the same manner, the league of Imam and Alfas in the state does not have the list of Islamic scholars needed for this study. However, based on

the interaction of the researcher with some of the identified Islamic scholars in the state, coupled with documentary evidence, the state has an average number of five hundred (500) scholars qualified to form the population of this study. The population of this study, therefore, stands at five hundred (500) people. Based on this, the study drew a sample of three hundred (300) Islamic scholars (*Alfas*)

Questionnaire Design

The researcher used a self-administered questionnaire. Questionnaire is considering appropriate for this study due to the following reasons: 1) It is a relatively cheaper and enhances the response rate (Sekaran, 2003); 2) There is no sensitive question involved in the study; 3) The questions are straightforward and easy to understand; 4) The scale used is easy to understand and manage; 5) Brief and clear written instructions were given

The questionnaire is distributed to the respondents who are living in Oyo State, Southwest, Nigeria and questionnaire are written in the English language. The questionnaire contains twenty-seven questions divided into 4 sections which are: A, B, C and D.

In section A, the question indicates the respondent's demographic profile like education level, gender, occupation, marital status and age. The objectives of this question are to know the correlation of the demography toward establishment of *waqf* institution towards poverty alleviation among Muslim *Ummah* in

Measurement and operationalization of variables

In this research, the dependent variable is the establishment of *waqf* as a way of Poverty alleviation. Meanwhile, the

across the thirty-three-local government of Oyo state, Nigeria. However, we select the sample size in a scientific way by following the recommendations of authorities. Krejcie and Morgan (1970) provide a table for the determination of sample size for a different population. The sample size correlates with the population of 500 is 217 (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970).

Southwest Nigeria. Section B indicates the respondent's perception of the establishment of *waqf* institution as a way of poverty alleviation. The questionnaire emanates from the measurement adapted from the literature. Specifically, a 5-point Likert scale questionnaire comprising strongly disagree (1), disagree (2), neutral (3), agree (4), and strongly agree (5) was used for the study. After that, this section is divided into 3 sections as follow:

- 1- Attitudes
- 2- Subjective Norm.
- 3- Perceived Behavioural Control.

Section C addresses how the establishment of *waqf* institution as a way of poverty alleviation is measured.

Lastly, section D provides a space for respondents to leave their comment, opinions, or suggestions for the establishment of *waqf* institution toward poverty alleviation among Muslim *Ummah*. These can be used to understand the user behaviour and their establishment towards *waqf* institution.

independent variables are attitudes, subjective norm and perceived behavioural control. The questionnaire items are adapted from previous studies.

Dependent Variables: Establishment of Waqf Institution as a way of Poverty Alleviation

Measured in this study using items adapted from Ramayah et al. (2009) and Gopi and Ramayah (2007). The variable is measured using a 5-point Likert scale questionnaire strongly disagree (1), disagree (2), neutral (3), agree (4), and strongly agree (5) will be used for the study. The items are presented as follows:

1. I will choose *waqf* institution as a way for poverty alleviation.

Independent Variable: Attitude

Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) defined attitude as an individual's behaviour towards awful or good activities. The scholars express that people's feeling, for example, negative or positive will influence the individual in playing out a specific behaviour.

Attitude is measured in this study using items adapted from Ramayah et al. (2009) and Gopi and Ramayah (2007). The variable is measured using a 5-point Likert scale questionnaire strongly disagree (1),

Independent Variable: Subjective Norm

Ajzen (1991) defined subjective norm as the perceived influence of friends or relatives with regards to whether the certain behaviour should be performed.

Subjective Norm is measured in this study using items adapted from Ramayah et al. (2009) and Gopi and Ramayah (2007). The variable is measured using a 5-point Likert scale questionnaire strongly disagree (1),

Independent Variable: Perceived Behavioural Control

Perceived behavioural control refers to the level of capacity and control which an individual perceives over performing the desired behaviour (Ajzen, 1991).

Perceived behavioural control (PBC) is measured in this study using items adapted from Shih and Fang (2004). The variable is

2. Overall, I plan to participate in *waqf* institution as a tool for poverty alleviation.
3. I will recommend *waqf* institution to my friends as a mechanism for poverty alleviation.
4. My general intention to participate in *waqf* is as an instrument for poverty alleviation.
5. I will think about opting for *waqf* as a tool for poverty alleviation.

disagree (2), neutral (3), agree (4), and strongly agree (5) will be used for the study. The items are presented as follows:

1. Waqf establishment is beneficial.
2. Participating in *waqf* institution is rewarding.
3. I have a positive perception of the establishment of *waqf* institutions.
4. Establishment of *waqf* institutions is a good idea.
5. I like the establishment of *waqf* institutions.

disagree (2), neutral (3), agree (4), and strongly agree (5) will be used for the study. The items are presented as follows:

1. Most people who are important to me think that I should participate in *waqf* institution establishments.
2. My friends think that I should be involved in *waqf* institution establishment.
3. I am expected to be involved in *waqf* institution establishment.

measured using a 5-point Likert scale questionnaire strongly disagree (1), disagree (2), neutral (3), agree (4), and strongly agree (5) will be used for the study. The items are presented as follows:

1. I have financial resources to partake in *waqf* institutions.
2. I have the ability to be involved in *waqf* institutions.

3. I have knowledge about *waqf* institutions.

4. Participating in *waqf* establishment is within my control.

This part explains the analysis of the data collected through questionnaire. The data were interpreted using SPSS version 22. The data analyses included descriptive statistics, while correlation analysis used in checking the degree of relationship that exists among the variables investigated in this paper and regression analysis was used

in examining the influence of distributed to the respondents Islamic Scholar (Alfas). However, a total of 218 questionnaires were retrieved and was used in the data analysis. This indicates that response rate was estimated of 72.6%. The details are summarized in the below Table 1.2.

Table 1.2
Response Rate and Data Collection

Items	Frequency	Percentage
Distributed Questionnaires	300	100.0
Returned Questionnaires	218	72.6
Questionnaires used for analysis	218	72.6

Demographic Analysis

In Table 1.3, respondent's demographic factors information which include age, gender, marital status, education level and occupation were explained. The result indicates that out of a total of 218 respondents, male respondents (96.3%) were higher than female (3.7). It is also observed that respondents that are less than 30 years of age 39.9%; those between 30 and 39 are 20.2%; 40-49 are 10.6%; 50-59 are 14.2%; while those between 60 and above constitute 15.1%.

Married respondents in the survey are 48.2%; single respondents are 26.6%, while others are 25.5%. On the basis of the level of education, respondents with primary education are 43.6% of the sample; those with secondary education constitute 11.9%; respondents with tertiary institution qualification take 18.3% of the sample population; while others are 26.1%. On the basis of respondent's occupation, civil services are 44.5%; those in business are 12.4%; farming (18.3%); self-employed (5.5%); academics/ teachers (19.3%).

Table 1.3 Demographic Data of respondents Profiles

	Frequency	Percent (%)
Gender		
Male	210	96.3
Female	8	3.7
Age		
Less than 30	87	39.9
30-39	44	20.2
40-49	23	10.6
50-59	31	14.2
60 and above	33	15.1
Marital status		
Married	105	48.2
Single	58	26.6

	55	25.2
Others		
Level of Education		
Primary	95	43.6
Secondary	26	19.3
Tertiary institution	40	18.3
Others	57	26.1
Occupation		
Civil servant	97	44.5
Business	27	12.4
Farming	40	18.3
Self-employed	12	5.5
Academic/teacher	42	19.3
Others		

Table 1.4

		Correlations			
		WAQAF	PBC	ATT	NORM
Pearson Correlation	WAQAF	1.000	.569	.427	.474
	PBC	.569	1.000	.458	.332
	ATT	.427	.458	1.000	.267
	NORM	.474	.332	.267	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	WAQAF	.	.000	.000	.000
	PBC	.000	.	.000	.000
	ATT	.000	.000	.	.000
	NORM	.000	.000	.000	.
N	WAQAF	218	218	218	218
	PBC	218	218	218	218
	ATT	218	218	218	218
	NORM	218	218	218	218

Note: PBC= perceived Behavioural Control, ATT= Attitude, SUB-NORM= Subjective Norm, *Waqf*.

Table 1.4 shows person correlation of that all variables examined. It is indicating that all the intercorrelation are significant. However, the coefficients of correlation are all below the threshold value of 8.0 this shows that the tendency of multicollinearity is low. Similarly, the

4 Method of Analysis

Statistical regression analysis is used to examine the hypotheses relating to the independent variables in this study.

Finding and Discussion

From the regression result displayed in table 1.4, the value of the coefficient of

result of variance inflation factor (VIF) report values of 1.290, 1.145 and 1.347 for attitude, subjective norm and perceived behavioural control respectively. This indicates that data was free from multicollinearity. Therefore, the data can be used for further analysis.

determination (R^2) is 43.6% signifying that the independent variable under consideration (attitude, subjective norm, perceived behavioural control) jointly explain 46.3% of the variance in the value of establishment of *waqf* institution as a way of poverty alleviation. Also, Durbin Watson value for this study is 2.303, which

falls between the accepted range of 1.5 and 2.5 is acceptable. (Lukacs, Burnham & Anderson, 2010). The purpose of checking Durbin Watson is to investigate the issue of auto-correlation. The value of 2.303 has

been demonstrated that this study is free from auto-correlation and sample error that might occur at random as the Durbin Wasson value falls within the acceptable value of 1.5 to 2.5.

Table 1.5

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		t	P. Value
	B	Std. Error		
(Constant)	4.014	1.698	2.363	.019
ATT	.204	.071	2.866	.005
NORM	.387	.071	5.430	.000
PBC	.350	.053	6.607	.000

Dependent variable is establishment of Waqf.

Table 1.5 indicates the results of analyses of survey data in the study on the significance of factors (attitude, subjective norm, perceived behavioural control) to influence the establishment of the *waqf* institution as a way of poverty alleviation. From this table, it is observed that all relationships are significant.

Hypothesis H1 stated that there is a positive significant relationship between attitude and establishment of the *waqf* institution as a way of poverty alleviation. The result ($\beta=.204$, $t=2.866$, $p \text{ value}=.005$) show that there is a positive and significant influence of attitude on establishment of the *waqf* institution as a way of poverty alleviation this indicates that the hypothesis is supported.

Hypothesis H2 stated that there is a positive significant relationship between subjective norm and establishment of the

waqf institution as a way of poverty alleviation. The result ($\beta=.387$, $t=5.430$, $p \text{ value}=.000$) show that there is a positive and significant influence of subjective norm on establishment of the *waqf* institution as a way of poverty alleviation this indicates that the hypothesis is supported.

Hypothesis H3 stated that there is a positive significant relationship between perceived behavioural control and establishment of the *waqf* institution as a way of poverty alleviation. The result ($\beta=.350$, $t=6.607$, $p \text{ value}=.000$) show that there is a positive and significant influence of perceived behavioural control on establishment of the *waqf* institution as a way of poverty alleviation this indicates that the hypothesis is supported.

Therefore, all hypotheses are supported and significantly.

Discussion

The study suggests that there is a positive significant relationship between attitude and establishment of the *waqf* institution as a way of poverty alleviation. Based on this, Ajzen (1991) viewed attitude as necessary things to predict and describe human action. Many studies conducted also show a significant positive relationship between action and attitude. Meanwhile, attitude

towards establishment of *waqf* indicates how Muslims view *waqf* as good or bad, will influence their decision to embrace the establishment of the *waqf* institution towards poverty alleviation. This research supports the previous studies such as of Shih and Fang, 2004; Lada *et al*, 2008; Amin and Chong 2011, that confirm that attitude significantly and positively

influence the establishment of *waqf* institution towards poverty alleviation. The result shows that there is positive significant relationship between subjective norm and establishment of the *waqf* institution as a way of poverty alleviation. This implies that the input, awareness or orientation given by those who know and value *waqf* institution can influence friends and people around in the society. This can go a long way in influencing those who are not well conversant with the *waqf* institution to embrace the idea of its establishment. The result of the research is consistent with the previous finding of Lada et al. (2008), and Amin & Chong (2011). The evidence found the relationship between subjective norm and establishment of the *waqf* institution as a way of poverty alleviation. This research finding indicates that subjective norm can

Limitation

Although this study was successful, there are various factors that limit its finding. The most important limitation is little literature available in the subject area. The study mostly focusses on Islamic religion perspective because the *waqf* is an Islamic principle that is understood by the Muslim. The study also involved particular respondents which is Islamic scholar in Oyo state in a particular location that is familiar with *waqf* and its application in the society. Therefore, the finding of the study cannot be generalized on others geographical states in south-west areas and the entire country (Nigeria). Future study can cover other parts of the country. The study makes a contribution to Oyo state government particularly Muslim Ummah in the state by providing guidelines and direction on establishment of *waqf* institution towards poverty alleviation. In addition, the study also provides the theoretical evidence for a future research. Generally, the study examined the contributing factors of the establishment of

give a significant and positive influence on establishment of the *waqf* institution as a way of poverty alleviation in Oyo state, south-west, Nigeria which is also in accordance with previous studies.

The result shows that there is a positive significant relationship between perceived behavioural control and establishment of the *waqf* institution as a way of poverty alleviation. The evidence found positive relationship between perceived behavioural control and establishment of the *waqf* institution as a way of poverty alleviation. This research supports the previous study of Noor Faezah (2014) that found that perceived behaviour control contributes in a significant and positive way in influencing the establishment of *waqf* institution towards poverty alleviation.

waqf institution towards poverty alleviation among Muslim Ummah in Oyo state south-west, Nigeria. The study has also contributed to the existing knowledge relating to the *waqf*. It is hoped similar research can be conducted in another area.

Recommendation

Arising from the discussion of finding elaborated earlier, the following recommendations are made:

- (1) Muslim in Oyo state should see the establishment of *waqf* institution as a necessity for the benefit of Muslim Ummah and mankind in general. The true practicality of *waqf* establishment can arguable lead to the poverty reduction, eradication and elimination.
- (2) Islamic scholar should organize workshop, seminar, conference and training with a view to enlighten people on the concept of *waqf* institution and how it can be used in dealing with poverty problem in the society.

(3) Also, Islamic scholar should create orientation and awareness to the wealthy people on how to meaningfully contribute to *waqf*

institution and the rewards accruable to them as prescribed by the Holy Quran.

Conclusion

In conclusion, according to the objective of the *study*, research question, general problem statement, related literature and analysis on data conducted, the objective of this paper is achieved. This research identified the factors that influence Muslim to establishment *waqf* institution towards poverty alleviation among Muslim *Ummah* in Oyo state, south-west, Nigeria. The factors are attitude, subjective norm and perceived behavioural control. the researcher adopted self-administered questionnaires to gather information from the respondents. *Waqf* is Islamic mechanism to alleviate poverty in a society that assists the needy. According to the literatures reviewed if Oyo state Muslim *Ummah* can embrace establishment of

waqf it will help them to assist underprivileged Muslim and reduce poverty in the state especially the current time that country faces recession problem, the *waqf* institution can be a foundation of financing for investment in the state, particularly for Islamic contracts like *Mudarabah*, *Musharakah*, *Murabaha*, *sukuk* and others in this aspect it would help to upgrade the investment in the state and the entire country at large. Similarly, the revenue generated from those investment could be utilized on programmes like poverty alleviation among others. This arguably would reduce poverty level among Muslim *Ummah* in the state which has always been an important matter.

REFERENCES

- AbulHasan, M. S. (2002). Waqf, perpetual charity and poverty alleviation. *International Journal of Social Economics*, 29(1/2), 135-151.
- Adeyonu, A. G., Oni, O. A., Okoruwa, V. O., & Omonona, B. T. (2012). Seasonality in Poverty Level of Rural Farming Households in Oyo State Nigeria. *ARPN Journal of Agricultural and Biological Science*, 7(8) 570-575.
- Ahmad Bello, D. (2009). Poverty Alleviation through Zakah and Waqf Institutions: A Case for the Muslim *Ummah* in Ghana. Paper Presented at the First National Muslim Summit organised by Al-Furqan Foundation, Tamale, Ghana, Held at Radach Memorial Centre, Lamashegu, Tamale, Ghana.
- Ahmed, U., Mohammed, M. O., Faosiy, O. A., & Daud, N. M. (2015). Examining the Perception of Muslim Community in Uganda on Waqf and its Role on Socio-Economic Development. *Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research*, 23(6), 1173-1180.
- Ali, I. B. (2009). Waqf: A sustainable development institution for Muslim communities. *Takaaful T&T Friendly Society, Trinidad and Tobago*, available at www.takaafultt.org.
- Amin, H., Rahim Abdul Rahman, A., & Ramayah, T. (2009). What makes undergraduate students enroll into an elective course? The case of Islamic accounting. *International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management*, 2(4), 289-304.

- Amin, H., & Chong, R. K. (2011). Is the theory of reasoned action valid for Ar-Rahnu? An empirical investigation. *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 5(10), 716-726.
- Ajzen, I., & Fishbein, M. (1980). Understanding attitudes and predicting social behaviour. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behaviour. *Organizational Behaviour and Human Decision Processes*, 50, 179-211. *De Young*, 509-526.
- Ajzen, I. (2002). Constructing a TPB questionnaire: Conceptual and methodological considerations. Retrieved online on 30th November 2016 from <http://www.unibielefeld.de/ikg/zick/aajzen%20construction%20a%20pb%20questionnaire.pdf>
- Armitage, C. J. (2005). Can the theory of planned behavior predict the maintenance of physical activity? *Health Psychology*, 24(3), 235.
- Baalbaki, R. (1988). Al-Mawrid. A Modern Arabic-English Dictionary, Dar El-ilm Iilmalayin, Beirut Lebanon.
- Bhattacharjee, A. (2000). Acceptance of e-commerce services: the case of electronic brokerages. *IEEE Transactions on systems, man, and cybernetics-Part A: Systems and humans*, 30(4), 411-420.
- Bremer, J. (2004, May). Islamic philanthropy: Reviving traditional forms for building social justice. *In CSID Fifth Annual Conference on "Defining and Establishing Justice in Muslim Societies*. University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill (U.S).
- Saifuddin, F., Kayadibi, S., Polat, R., Fidan, Y., & Kayadibi, O. (2014). The Role of cash Waqf in poverty alleviation: Case of Malaysia. *International Journal of Business, Economics and Law*, 4 (1), 171-179.
- Cavana, R. Y., Delahaye, B. L., & Sekaran, U. (2001). *Applied business research: Qualitative and quantitative methods*. John Wiley & Sons Australia, Milton, Queensland.
- Cizakca, M. (1998). "Awqaf in History and Its Implications for Modern Islamic Economies". *Islamic Economic Studies*, Vol. 6, No. 1, (Jeddah: IRTI & IDB).
- Fauziah, Taib, M., Ramayah, T., & Abdul Razak, D. (2008). Factors influencing intention to use diminishing partnership home financing. *International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management*, 1(3), 235-248.
- Fishbein, M., & Ajzen, I. (1975). *Belief, Attitude, Intention and Behavior: An Introduction to Theory and Research Reading*, MA: Addison-Wesley.
- Foyasal Khan, (2010) Waqf: An Islamic Instrument of Poverty Alleviation-Bangladesh Perspective, Seventh International Conference- *The Tawhild Epistemology: Zakat and Waqf Economy*, Bangi.
- Gopi, M., & Ramayah, T. (2007). Applicability of theory of planned behavior in predicting intention to trade online: Some evidence from a developing country. *International Journal of Emerging Markets*, 2(4) 348-360.
- Hisham, Y (2013). Waqf History and Legislation in Malaysia: A contemporary perspective. *Journal of Islamic and Human Advanced Research*, Vol. 3, Issue 6, month 2013.
- Jalil, A. and Asharaf Mohd Ramli (2008). *Waqf Instruments for Construction*

- contract: An analysis of structure. *The Journal of Muamalat and Islamic Finance Research (JMIFR)*, 5(1), 14.
- John, O. A., & Bright, O. O. (2012). Poverty and youth unemployment in Nigeria, 1987-2011. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3(20).
- Kahf, M. (1998). *Financing the development of Awqaf property*. A paper prepared for the seminar on Development of Awqaf organized by IRTI, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, from March 2-4.
- Kazeem, Y. (2018). Nigeria is set to stay the world's poverty capital for at least a generation, Quartz Africa. <https://qz.com/africa/1421543/nigeria-poverty-crisis-is-worsening-oxfam-world-bank-data/>
- Keyton, J. (2015). *Communication research: Asking questions, finding answers*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Khan, M. T. (n.d) Contribution of Islamic Waqf in Poverty Reduction. Retrieved online on 17th April 2016 from <http://pide.org.pk/psde/pdf/AGM30/papers/Contribution%20of%20Islamic%20Waqf%20in%20Poverty%20Reduction.pdf>
- Kothari, C. R. (2004). *Research methodology: Methods and techniques*. New Delhi: Age International.
- Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Table for determining sample size from a given population. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 30(3), 607-610.
- Lada, C. J., Muench, A. A., Rathborne, J., Alves, J. F., & Lombardi, M. (2008). The nature of the dense core population in the Pipe Nebula: thermal cores under pressure. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 672(1), 410.
- Lukacs, P. M., Burnham, K. P., & Anderson, D. R. (2010). Model selection bias and Freedman's paradox. *Annals of the Institute of Statistical Mathematics*, 62(1), 117-125.
- Mannan M.A (2005) The Role of Waqf in Improving the Ummah Welfare. Presentation at the International Seminar on Islamic Economics as Solution organized by Indonesian Association of Islamic Economists and Muamalat Institute, Jakarta, Medan, Indonesia.
- Mardziyah, M. I. (2014). *The acceptance of online waqf in islamic banking institutions*. A Master thesis submitted to Othman Yeop Abdullah Graduate School of Business, University Utara Malaysia.
- Marczyk, G., DeMatteo, D., & Festinger, D. (2005). *Essentials of research design and methodology*. John Wiley & Sons Inc.
- Magda Ismail A. Momhsin (2014) Roundtable discussion on development of waqf properties in Malaysia, what can we do with waqf property?
- Monzer, K. (2003, January). The role of waqf in improving the ummah welfare. In *International Seminar on Waqf as a Private Legal Body, organised by the Islamic University of North Sumatra*, Medan, Indonesia Jan.
- Mustafa, O., & Ogunbado, A. F. (2015). Examining the Traditional Waqf-Based Financing Methods and Their Implications on Socio-Economic Development.
- National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) (2010). *The Nigeria poverty profile 2010 report*. Being a press briefing by the Statistician-General of the Federation/Chief Executive Officer, National Bureau of

- Statistics, Dr Yemi Kale held at the conference room, 5th floor, NBS headquarters, Central Business District, Abuja on Monday, 13th February 2012.
- Noor Faezah, B. B (2014). *The acceptance of waqf institutions establishment in UUM*. A Master thesis submitted to Othman Yeop Abdullah Graduate School of Business, University Utara Malaysia.
- Nour, H. M. H. M., & Hassan, M. (2012). Awqaf and heritage: urban conservation in historic muslim cities. The case of Waqf Institution in historic Cairo.
- Ogunbado, A. F. (2013). Islam and its Impact in Yorubaland. *The Islamic quarterly*, 57(1), 1-18.
- Okoroafor, M. O., & Nwaeze, C. (2013). Poverty and economic growth in Nigeria 1990-2011. *The Macrotheme Review*, 2(6), 105-115.
- Osman, A.F, (2014). An Analysis of Cash Waqf Participation Among Young Intellectual. *Paper published in Book Article. Waqf Iqlimi*. Universiti Sains Islam Malaysia.
- Osman, A. Z. (2012). *Accountability in managing waqf properties: the case of two State Religious Councils in Malaysia*. Thesis submitted to the university of London for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy, school of management, royal Holloway University of London.
- Ramayah, T., Rouibah, K., Gopi, M., & Rangel, G.J. (2009). A decomposed theory of reasoned action to explain intention to use Internet stock trading among Malaysia investors. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 25(6), 1222-1230.
- Sekaran, U. (2003). *Research methods for business: A skill building approach*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Shih, Y. Y., & Fang, K. (2004). The use of a decomposed theory of planned behavior to study Internet banking in Taiwan. *Internet Research*, 14(3), 213-223.
- UNESCO (2016). Poverty. Retrieved online on 23rd April 2016 from <http://www.unesco.org/new/en/social-and-human-sciences/themes/international-migration/glossary/poverty/>
- Uzoh, B. C., (2016). Poverty–Conflict Nexus: The Nigerian Experience. *The International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Invention*. 3(10), 2832-2838
- Vanguard newspaper (2015). *Over 100m Nigerians living below poverty line- Osinbajo*. Retrieved on 15th April 2016 from <http://www.vanguardngr.com/2015/08/over-1-million-nigerians-living-below-poverty-line-osinbajo/>
- Vanguard newspaper (2014). *Nigeria, third on world poverty index- World Bank*. Retrieved online on 15th April 2016 from <http://www.vanguardngr.com/2014/04/440695/>
- World Bank (2017) <https://qz.com/963465/some-of-the-worlds-biggest-countries-have-managed-to-wrangle-extreme-poverty-except-nigeria/>
- World Bank group (2017). Atlas of Sustainable Development Goals from World Development Indicators. Retrieved from: <file:///C:/Users/ibraheem/Downloads/9781464810800.pdf>
- Yusuff, J. A., & Noor Aziza, C. E. (2013). Alleviation of poverty among OIC countries through sadaqat, cash waqf and public funding. *International Journal of Trade, Economics and Finance*, 4(6), 403